

Temporal Dynamics of Rhizosphere Soil Physicochemical Properties in *Sorghum bicolor* Under Salinity and Drought Stress

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Abstract

This study evaluated the effects of salinity and drought stress on rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties of sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L.) across developmental stages to identify the major factors associated with soil variability during plant growth. Rhizospheric soil samples were collected from healthy, salinity-stressed, and drought-stressed sorghum plants at germination, 7, 14, 21, and 35 days after germination (DAG). Soil pH, electrical conductivity (EC), organic carbon (OC), and available nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K) were determined. Temporal variation and treatment effects were assessed using PERMANOVA, Pearson correlation analysis, principal component analysis (PCA), and hierarchical clustering.

Temporal profiling revealed stage-dependent changes in nutrient availability, EC, and OC, whereas soil pH remained comparatively stable. PERMANOVA identified developmental stage as the primary source of variation in rhizospheric soil properties, explaining 55.9% of the total variability ($p = 0.024$), while treatment effects were not significant. Correlation analysis showed a significant positive association between pH and available N ($r = 0.615$, $p = 0.033$), whereas most other relationships were weak to moderate. PCA and hierarchical clustering consistently identified pH, N, EC, OC and K as major contributors to rhizospheric variability. Coordinated

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variation among EC, OC and K and the relatively independent behavior of P were evident across analyses. Substantial overlap among treatment groups further indicated limited treatment-specific separation of overall soil physicochemical characteristics.

Developmental-stage-dependent changes were more strongly associated with rhizospheric soil variability than salinity or drought treatments, which produced comparatively modest modifications in soil physicochemical properties.

Keywords: *Sorghum bicolor*; rhizosphere; salinity stress; drought stress; soil physicochemical properties; PERMANOVA; principal component analysis; hierarchical clustering.

Introduction

Soil health is a key determinant of agricultural productivity and sustainability, particularly under increasing environmental constraints such as salinity and drought. These abiotic stresses can modify soil physicochemical properties, nutrient availability, and microbial activity, ultimately influencing plant growth and yield. Among cereal crops, sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L.) is well known for its adaptability to adverse environments, including water deficit and saline conditions, making it a valuable model for investigating stress responses in arid and semi-arid regions (Abuslima et al., 2022; Dewi et al., 2023).

Salinity stress is a widespread environmental challenge that disrupts soil ionic balance and elevates electrical conductivity (EC), resulting in osmotic stress and ion toxicity. High salt concentrations in the rhizosphere interfere with nutrient uptake, particularly potassium (K^+), because of competition with sodium (Na^+), thereby affecting essential physiological processes in plants (Dourado et al., 2022; Rajabi Dehnavi et al., 2024). In contrast, drought stress primarily affects soil biological processes by reducing moisture availability, limiting microbial activity, and suppressing nutrient mineralization. Consequently, the availability of essential nutrients, including nitrogen (N) and organic carbon (OC), may decline, negatively impacting soil fertility and plant performance (Avila et al., 2023; Silva et al., 2023).

The rhizosphere is a highly dynamic zone where plant roots, soil microorganisms, and soil physicochemical properties interact to regulate nutrient cycling and stress adaptation. These soil–plant–microbe interactions are fundamental for maintaining soil biological fertility and ecosystem functioning (Bhattacharyya and Furtak, 2022). Recent studies have shown that salinity and drought can alter rhizosphere microbial composition and functionality, thereby influencing plant health and resilience (Qi et al., 2022; Wei et al., 2023).

nutrient cycling in soil is governed by interconnected biogeochemical processes involving microbial activity, organic matter turnover, and mineral transformations. Nitrogen cycling is particularly important because it determines the availability of plant-accessible nitrogen required for growth and productivity (Hayashi, 2022). Furthermore, soil carbon and nutrient cycles are closely linked with redox reactions and mineral interactions, which influence nutrient dynamics under environmental stress (Song et al., 2022; Najdenko et al., 2024; Kunito et al., 2024).

Recent reviews have highlighted the importance of integrated soil health indicators, including EC, pH, organic carbon, and nutrient availability, for evaluating soil quality and resilience under changing environmental conditions (Bhaduri et al., 2022; Bekchanova et al., 2024). However, nutrient cycling processes are highly sensitive to environmental disturbances, and their disruption can significantly affect ecosystem functioning and crop productivity (Xing et al., 2022; Drinkwater and Snapp, 2022). In addition, plant developmental stages influence rhizospheric processes through changes in root exudation and microbial activity, resulting in stage-specific shifts in soil properties. Despite this, most studies have focused on single time-point assessments, limiting understanding of temporal soil responses throughout plant development (Qi et al., 2022).

Therefore, this study investigated temporal variations in rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties and nutrient dynamics of sorghum under salinity and drought stress. By integrating time-course observations with multivariate statistical analyses, the study provides

insights into soil responses to abiotic stress and contributes to the development of sustainable crop and soil management strategies.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Design and Sample Collection

A controlled experiment was conducted in pots to evaluate the temporal dynamics of rhizospheric soil properties in sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*) under different stress conditions. Three treatments were considered: healthy (control), salinity stress and drought stress. Soil samples were collected from the rhizosphere at five developmental stages, namely germination (baseline), 7 days after germination (7 DAG), 14 DAG, 21 DAG, and 35 DAG. The germination stage represented a common baseline for all treatments prior to stress imposition.

Soil Physicochemical Analysis

Collected soil samples were analyzed for key physicochemical parameters following standard protocols. Soil pH was measured using a digital pH meter in a soil (Systronics, India) water suspension. Electrical conductivity (EC) was determined using a conductivity meter (Systronics, India). Organic carbon (OC) were estimated using standard oxidation methods as per the protocol of Walkley and Black et al., 1934. Available macronutrients, including nitrogen (N) (Subbiah and Asija et al., 1956), phosphorus (P) (Olsen et al. 1954; Spectrophotometer, Shimadzu, Japan) and potassium (K) (Hanway and Heidel et al., 1952; Flame Photometer 1027, Systronics, India), were quantified using established soil analysis procedures.

Temporal Analysis of Rhizospheric Soil Properties

Temporal variation in rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties was evaluated across developmental stages of *Sorghum bicolor* under healthy, salinity and drought treatments. Soil samples were collected at germination (baseline), 7, 14, 21 and 35 days after germination

(DAG). The measured variables included soil pH, electrical conductivity (EC), organic carbon (OC), available nitrogen (N), available phosphorus (P) and available potassium (K).

Line plots were generated using the ggplot2 package in R to visualize temporal changes in each parameter across treatments. The germination-stage sample was considered the baseline condition prior to stress imposition, whereas treatment-specific trends were assessed from 7 DAG onwards. Temporal patterns were interpreted qualitatively to identify treatment-dependent shifts in soil physicochemical properties during plant development.

Permutational Multivariate Analysis of Variance (PERMANOVA)

Euclidean distance matrices were calculated from the soil physicochemical data and significance was assessed using 999 permutations. The independent contributions of treatment and developmental stage were evaluated using marginal tests. To verify the assumption of homogeneous multivariate dispersion among groups, a multivariate dispersion analysis (PERMDISP) followed by a permutation test (999 permutations) was conducted. The germination sample was excluded from the analysis because it represented the common pre-treatment baseline.

Pearson Correlation Analysis

Pearson correlation analysis was performed by excluding the germination stage samples. Pearson correlation coefficients (r) and their associated significance levels (p -values) were calculated using the Hmisc package in R. Correlation matrices were visualized using both correlation plots and heatmaps to facilitate identification of positive and negative associations among soil variables. Correlation coefficients were interpreted according to their magnitude and direction and statistical significance was considered at $p < 0.05$.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

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Principal component analysis (PCA) was performed to explore multivariate variation by retaining germination-stage sample. Prior to analysis, all variables were centered and scaled to unit variance to eliminate differences in measurement units. PCA was conducted using the prompt function in R. The proportion of variance explained by each principal component was evaluated using eigenvalues and scree plots. Sample relationships were visualized through PCA score plots and treatment-specific confidence ellipses, while variable contributions and associations with sample groups were examined using PCA biplots. Ninety-five percent confidence ellipses (ellipse.level = 0.95) assuming a normal distribution were calculated and overlaid to evaluate group separation.

Hierarchical Clustering and Heatmap Analysis

Hierarchical clustering analysis (HCA) was performed by retaining germination stage sample. Prior to clustering, variables were standardized using Z-score normalization to remove differences in measurement scales. Euclidean distance was used to calculate pairwise dissimilarities among samples and variables and clustering was performed using Ward's minimum variance method (Ward.D2). Results were visualized as a heatmap with hierarchical dendrograms generated using the pheatmap package in R. Red colours indicate values above the overall mean, whereas blue colours indicate values below the mean.

Software Environment

All statistical analyses and graphical visualizations were performed in R (Version 4.4.2, R Core Team, 2025). The packages readxl (Wickham and Bryan, 2019), (FactoMineR (Le et al., 2008), factoextra (Kassambara and Mundt, 2016), pheatmap (Kolde et al., 2019), ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016), Hmisc (Harrell Jr and Dupont, 2020), corrplot (Wei and Simko, 2010), vegan (Oksanen et al., 2001) and RColorBrewer (Neuwirth, 2014). 2025) were used for multivariate analysis, correlation analysis, PCA visualization, heatmap generation, graphical customization and hierarchical clustering.

Results

The rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties measured across developmental stages under healthy, salinity and drought treatments are presented in Table 1.

SAMPLE	pH	EC	OC	N	P	K
G	7.93	0.739	0.52	222.656	34.575	206.416
H_7DAG	8.01	0.735	0.3	203.84	26.385	235.872
H_14DAG	8.06	0.544	0.33	175.616	54.87	206.416
H_21DAG	8.09	0.497	0.27	222.656	41.7225	202.048
H_35DAG	8.07	0.754	0.46	222.656	59.9775	198.128
S_7DAG	8.03	1.244	0.41	225.792	30.0975	229.6
S_14DAG	7.87	1.43	0.63	163.072	39.5175	223.552
S_21DAG	7.95	0.671	0.49	216.384	39.2925	198.464
S_35DAG	7.86	0.651	0.46	194.432	33.1725	179.2
D_7DAG	8.06	0.673	0.55	222.656	55.62	229.6
D_14DAG	7.93	0.586	0.41	200.704	51.72	208.656
D_21DAG	7.87	0.7	0.19	175.616	54.615	184.352
D_35DAG	8.02	0.724	0.22	194.432	28.2525	182.224

Table 1. Rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties of *Sorghum bicolor* under healthy, salinity, and drought treatments at different developmental stages.

*G = germination (baseline); H = healthy; S = salinity; D = drought; DAG = days after germination; EC = electrical conductivity (mS cm^{-1}); OC = organic carbon (%); N = available nitrogen (kg ha^{-1}); P = available phosphorus (kg ha^{-1}); K = available potassium (kg ha^{-1}). The germination sample was included as a common baseline reference for all treatments.

Temporal Variation in Physiochemical Parameters

Soil pH remained within a relatively narrow range throughout the experiment; however, healthy plants showed a generally increasing pH trend, whereas salinity- and drought-treated plants exhibited fluctuating responses across developmental stages. Electrical conductivity (EC) was consistently higher under salinity treatment, while healthy and drought treatments showed comparatively smaller fluctuations over time (figure S1)

Figure S1. Temporal variation in rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties of *Sorghum bicolor* under healthy, salinity, and drought treatments across developmental stages. Panels represent (a) pH, (b) electrical conductivity (EC), (c) organic carbon (OC), (d) organic carbon percentage (OC%), (e) available nitrogen (N), (f) available phosphorus (P), and (g) available potassium (K). The germination-stage sample represents the baseline condition prior to stress imposition. Lines connect measurements across developmental stages (7, 14, 21, and 35 DAG) for each treatment, illustrating temporal changes in soil nutrient status and physicochemical characteristics under abiotic stress.

Organic carbon (OC) displayed treatment-dependent variation. Drought-treated samples showed a progressive decline in OC from 7 to 35 DAG, whereas healthy and salinity-treated samples exhibited fluctuating patterns across developmental stages. Available nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) showed variable responses throughout plant development with no consistent increasing or decreasing trend across treatments. In contrast, available potassium (K) increased from 7 to 21 DAG in all treatments, followed by a decline at 35 DAG.

PERMANOVA and Multivariate Dispersion Analysis

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PERMANOVA revealed that developmental stage significantly influenced the multivariate rhizospheric soil physicochemical profile, explaining 55.907% of the total variation ($R^2 = 0.55907$; $F = 2.941$; $p = 0.024$; Table 2). In contrast, treatment accounted for only 6.077% of the variation and did not significantly affect the overall soil physicochemical composition ($R^2 = 0.06077$; $F = 0.4795$; $p = 0.829$). Residual variation accounted for 38.02% of the total variance.

The multivariate dispersion analysis indicated no significant differences in within-group dispersion among treatments (PERMDISP: $F = 0.087$, $p = 0.917$). This result was further confirmed by permutation testing ($p = 0.911$), demonstrating that group dispersions were comparable and that the PERMANOVA results were not influenced by unequal variability among treatments (Table S1, S2 and S3).

	Df	Sum of Sqs	R2	F-value	p-value
Treatment	2	660.3	0.06077	0.4795	0.829
Time	3	6075.2	0.55907	2.9413	0.024 *
Residual	6	4131	0.38016	-	-
Total	11	10866.6	1	-	-

Table 2. Marginal PERMANOVA assessing the independent contributions of treatment and developmental stage to variation in rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties of *Sorghum bicolor*.

*PERMANOVA was performed using Euclidean distances with 999 permutations using the marginal testing approach (adonis2, by = "margin"). R^2 values represent the proportion of total variation explained independently by each factor. Germination-stage samples were excluded prior to analysis. Significant effects are indicated by $p < 0.05$.

Source	Df	Sum of Squares	R ²	F-value	p-value
Model	5	6735.56	0.62	1.957	0.088

Residual	6	4131.04	0.38	–	–
Total	11	10866.6	1	–	–

Table S1. Permutational multivariate analysis of variance (PERMANOVA) evaluating the overall effects of treatment and developmental stage on rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties of *Sorghum bicolor*.

*PERMANOVA was performed using Euclidean distances. Significance was assessed using 999 permutations. R^2 represents the proportion of total multivariate variation explained by the model. Germination-stage samples were excluded prior to analysis.

Source	Df	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F-value	p-value
Groups	2	45.79	22.89	0.087	0.917
Residuals	9	2365.67	262.85	–	–

Table S2. Multivariate dispersion analysis (PERMDISP)

*Homogeneity of multivariate dispersions among treatment groups was assessed using Euclidean distances.

Source	Df	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F-value	Permutations	p-value
Groups	2	45.79	22.89	0.087	999	0.911
Residuals	9	2365.67	262.85	–	–	–

Table S3. Permutation test for multivariate dispersion

*Significance was assessed using 999 unrestricted permutations.

Correlation Analysis

Pearson correlation analysis revealed generally weak to moderate associations among rhizospheric soil properties (Table 3; Fig. 1). Among all pairwise relationships, only the

correlation between pH and available nitrogen was statistically significant, exhibiting a moderate positive association ($r = 0.615$, $p = 0.033$). This indicates that higher soil pH values were associated with increased nitrogen availability across treatments and developmental stages.

Physiochemical Parameters	pH	EC	OC	N	P	K
pH	-	-0.28544	-0.19391	0.615018	0.140373	0.307672
EC	0.368485	-	0.485178	-0.22069	-0.3213	0.442245
OC	0.545931	0.109856	-	0.072083	0.132642	0.395974
N	0.033305	0.490651	0.823832	-	-0.04079	0.218736
P	0.663468	0.308513	0.681114	0.89983	-	-0.10608
K	0.330623	0.149992	0.202588	0.494599	0.742827	-

Table 3. Pearson correlation coefficients (above diagonal) and p-values (below diagonal) among rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties

*EC = electrical conductivity (mS cm^{-1}); OC = organic carbon (%); N = available nitrogen (kg ha^{-1}); P = available phosphorus (kg ha^{-1}); K = available potassium (kg ha^{-1}). Significant correlations criteria used ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 1. Pearson correlation heatmap showing pairwise relationships among rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties. Cell values represent correlation coefficients (r), with red and blue colors indicating positive and negative correlations, respectively.

Electrical conductivity showed moderate positive correlations with organic carbon ($r = 0.485$, $p = 0.1098$) and potassium ($r = 0.442$, $p = 0.1499$) and moderate negative correlations with pH ($r = -0.285$, $p = 0.368$), nitrogen ($r = -0.2206$, $p = 0.4906$) and phosphorus ($r = -0.321$, $p = 0.3085$), although these relationships were not statistically significant. Organic carbon exhibited weak positive associations with nitrogen ($r = 0.0720$, $p = 0.8238$), phosphorus ($r = 0.1326$, $p = 0.6811$) and potassium ($r = 0.3959$, $p = 0.2025$), suggesting a potential linkage between soil carbon status and nutrient availability. Phosphorus displayed consistently weak correlations with all other measured variables, indicating relative independence from the measured physicochemical properties (Supplementary fig. S2)

Figure S2. Pearson correlation heatmap showing pairwise relationships among rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties. Color intensity and cell values represent the magnitude and direction of Pearson correlation coefficients (r).

The correlation heatmap and matrix further confirmed the predominance of weak-to-moderate associations among variables with the strongest positive relationship observed between

pH and nitrogen and the strongest negative relationship observed between EC and phosphorus. Ultimately, the correlation structure suggests direct links between most soil properties appear limited and pH may be the primary variable influencing nitrogen availability in the sorghum rhizosphere.

Principal Component Analysis

Principal component analysis revealed that the first two principal components explained 61.37% of the total variation in rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties, with PC1 accounting for 32.43% and PC2 accounting for 28.94% of the variance. Inclusion of PC3 increased the cumulative explained variance to 79.19%, indicating that the first three components adequately represented the major patterns in the dataset. The scree plot showed a marked decline in variance explained after PC3, suggesting that subsequent components contributed relatively little additional information (Table 4; Fig.2, Supplementary Fig. S3, S4)

	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5	PC6
Standard deviation	1.3949	1.3177	1.0341	0.8633	0.56112	0.43396
Proportion of Variance	0.3243	0.2894	0.1782	0.1242	0.05248	0.03139
Cumulative Proportion	0.3243	0.6137	0.7919	0.9161	0.96861	1

Table 4. Variance explained by principal components derived from PCA of rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties.

*PCA was conducted using pH, EC, OC, N, P, and K. The proportion of variance shows the contribution of each principal component to total variability, while the cumulative proportion indicates the total variance explained by successive components. The first three principal components explained 79.19% of the total variation.

Figure 2. Principal component analysis (PCA) biplot of rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties in *Sorghum bicolor* under healthy, salinity, and drought treatments. Samples represent developmental stages, while arrows indicate the direction and magnitude of variable contributions to sample separation. Principal components were calculated using standardized soil physicochemical variables. The percentages shown on the axes indicate the proportion of total variance explained by each principal component. Samples positioned closer together exhibit greater similarity in their overall soil physicochemical characteristics, whereas variables with longer vectors contribute more strongly to sample separation.

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Figure S3.Scree plot showing the percentage of variance explained by the first six principal components derived from rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties of *Sorghum bicolor*. Bars represent the variance explained by individual principal components, while the line illustrates the cumulative decline in explained variance across successive components.

The PCA score plot demonstrated distinct treatment-dependent variation in rhizospheric soil properties (Supplementary Fig. S4).

Figure S4.PCA individuals (score) plot of rhizospheric soil samples of *Sorghum bicolor*. Samples are projected onto PC1 (32.4%) and PC2 (28.9%), with ellipses indicating treatment-wise clustering patterns and multivariate variation among developmental stages and stress treatments.

The germination-stage sample occupied a central position, reflecting the common baseline condition prior to stress exposure. Healthy samples clustered closely together on the positive side of PC1, indicating comparatively stable soil physicochemical characteristics

throughout plant development. Drought-treated samples exhibited moderate dispersion and progressive separation across developmental stages, whereas salinity-treated samples displayed the widest distribution, particularly along PC1, indicating greater heterogeneity in rhizospheric responses under salt stress (Supplementary Fig. S5).

Figure S5. Labelled principal component analysis (PCA) score plot of rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties under healthy, salinity, and drought treatments. Each point represents an individual soil sample and is labelled according to treatment and developmental stage. Samples are coloured by treatment group and ellipses represent the 95% confidence intervals of each group. The plot illustrates the distribution and similarity of samples based on soil pH, electrical conductivity (EC), organic carbon (OC) and available nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P) and potassium (K). Healthy samples clustered relatively closely, whereas salinity-treated samples showed greater dispersion. Drought-treated samples exhibited intermediate variability. The

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substantial overlap among treatment ellipses indicates limited treatment-specific separation of overall rhizospheric soil physicochemical characteristics.

The PCA biplot showed that pH and available nitrogen (N) were positively associated, as indicated by their similar vector orientation toward the positive side of both PC1 and PC2 (Fig. 2). In contrast, electrical conductivity (EC) was oriented in the opposite direction, suggesting an inverse relationship with pH and N. Organic carbon (OC) and potassium (K) were aligned toward the upper-left quadrant, indicating coordinated variation between these variables, whereas phosphorus (P) was primarily associated with variation along PC1. The distribution of samples showed substantial overlap among treatment groups, indicating limited treatment-specific separation in overall rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties (Supplementary Fig. S5).

Hierarchical Clustering Analysis

The hierarchical clustering heatmap revealed distinct patterns of similarity among rhizospheric soil samples and physicochemical variables. Sample clustering did not occur strictly according to treatment, indicating substantial overlap in overall soil physicochemical profiles among healthy, salinity and drought conditions. Nevertheless, several treatment-specific subclusters were evident. Salinity-treated samples, particularly S_7DAG and S_14DAG, clustered closely together and were characterized by elevated EC, OC, and K values. In contrast, healthy samples from later developmental stages formed a separate cluster associated with comparatively higher pH and phosphorus levels (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Hierarchical clustering heatmap showing patterns of variation in rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties under healthy, salinity, and drought treatments of *Sorghum bicolor*. Rows represent individual samples and columns represent soil variables. Samples and variables were clustered using Euclidean distance and Ward’s linkage method. Color intensity indicates the relative standardized abundance of each parameter, with red representing higher values and blue representing lower values.

The variable dendrogram identified two major groups of soil properties. EC, OC and K clustered together, indicating coordinated variation among soil ionic status, organic carbon content and potassium availability. A second cluster comprised pH, N and P, may suggesting close relationships among nutrient availability and soil chemical balance. The clustering pattern indicates that variables within each group responded similarly across treatments and developmental stages.

The heatmap demonstrates that rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties were structured by complex interactions among nutrient availability, soil ionic status and carbon dynamics rather than by treatment alone.

Discussion:

Temporal Variation in Physicochemical Parameters

The contrasting temporal responses of individual soil properties indicate that abiotic stress influenced specific components of the rhizospheric environment rather than producing uniform changes across all measured variables. The consistently higher EC observed under salinity treatment reflects the direct effect of salt addition on soil ionic status (Liu, 2015), whereas the relatively stable pH across treatments suggests that soil acidity-alkalinity was less sensitive to the imposed stresses.

The progressive decline in organic carbon under drought indicates a sustained reduction in soil carbon status during plant development, while the more variable responses under healthy and salinity conditions suggest greater temporal fluctuation in carbon availability. In contrast, the absence of clear trends for nitrogen and phosphorus implies that their availability was influenced by multiple factors operating across developmental stages rather than by treatment alone.

The similar potassium pattern observed across all treatments, characterized by an increase up to 21 DAG followed by a decline at 35 DAG, suggests a stronger association with plant developmental stage than with stress treatment. The observed temporal patterns support the view that developmental-stage-dependent changes contributed substantially to variation in rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties, while salinity and drought primarily affected specific variables rather than the overall soil profile.

PERMANOVA

The PERMANOVA results indicate that developmental stage was the primary factor shaping rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties, whereas salinity and drought treatments had comparatively limited effects on the overall multivariate soil profile. The significant contribution of developmental stage suggests that changes associated with plant growth and rhizosphere development exerted a stronger influence on soil chemistry than the imposed stress

treatments. As sorghum progressed from early vegetative growth to later developmental stages, alterations in nutrient uptake, root exudation patterns, microbial activity and rhizosphere nutrient transformations likely contributed to the observed temporal variation (Philippot et al., 2013; Prashar et al., 2014).

This finding suggests that treatment-induced changes were more subtle than the temporal shifts associated with plant development. The non-significant PERMDISP results further strengthen this interpretation by confirming that the observed multivariate patterns were not artifacts of unequal dispersion among treatment groups.

Correlation Analysis

The significant positive correlation between pH and available nitrogen suggests that soil chemical conditions played an important role in regulating nitrogen availability within the sorghosphere. In alkaline soils, slight variations in pH can influence microbial mineralization processes and nitrogen transformation pathways, thereby affecting the pool of plant-available nitrogen (Marschner, 2012; Paul, 2015). The positive association observed in this study indicates that higher pH conditions may have favoured nitrogen availability during plant development.

Although not statistically significant, the moderate positive relationships between EC, organic carbon and potassium indicate potential interactions among soil ionic status, carbon dynamics and nutrient availability across developmental stages and stress treatments. The positive association between EC and potassium is biologically plausible because potassium contributes to osmotic regulation and ionic balance, particularly under stress conditions (Wang et al., 2013; Hasanuzzaman et al., 2018). Similarly, the association between organic carbon and nutrient variables may reflect the role of soil organic matter in nutrient storage and rhizosphere functioning (Magdoff and Weil, 2004).

Phosphorus exhibited weak correlations with all measured soil properties, suggesting that its availability was influenced by factors not directly captured by the analyzed physicochemical variables. In alkaline soils, phosphorus availability is often governed by precipitation reactions, adsorption processes and localized rhizosphere interactions rather than broad changes in soil chemistry (Marschner, 2012; Brady and Weil, 2016).

The correlation analysis indicates that the measured soil properties were largely independent of one another with pH representing the most influential factor associated with nitrogen availability. These findings suggest that abiotic stress may influence rhizospheric nutrient dynamics through complex and multifactorial processes rather than through strong direct interactions among individual soil physicochemical parameters.

Principal Component Analysis

Principal component analysis revealed that variation in rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties was primarily associated with relationships among soil nutrients, ionic status and carbon dynamics rather than with distinct treatment-specific separation. The close alignment of pH and available nitrogen vectors indicates a strong positive association between these variables, consistent with the correlation analysis. This relationship likely reflects the influence of soil chemical conditions on nitrogen availability and nitrogen transformation processes (Marschner, 2012; Paul, 2015).

Electrical conductivity was oriented in the opposite direction to pH and nitrogen, suggesting that increased soil ionic content was associated with changes in nutrient dynamics. This pattern is biologically reasonable under salinity stress, where the accumulation of soluble salts can alter nutrient availability and rhizosphere chemical balance (Rietz and Haynes, 2003; Wang et al., 2013). Organic carbon and potassium exhibited similar vector orientations, indicating coordinated variation between soil carbon status and potassium availability. Potassium plays a critical role in osmotic regulation and stress adaptation while soil organic carbon

influences nutrient retention and rhizosphere functioning, potentially explaining their association (Wang et al., 2013; Hasanuzzaman et al., 2018; Magdoff and Weil, 2004).

Phosphorus showed a distinct orientation along the first principal component, indicating that its variation was partly independent of the patterns observed for nitrogen, potassium and organic carbon. This suggests that phosphorus dynamics were regulated by additional soil processes, including adsorption-desorption reactions and pH-dependent availability (Marschner, 2012; Brady and Weil, 2016).

Despite some dispersion among treatment groups, substantial overlap of the confidence ellipses was observed, indicating limited separation of healthy, drought and salinity treatments based on overall soil physicochemical characteristics. This interpretation is supported by PERMANOVA which identified developmental stage as the primary source of multivariate variation, whereas treatment effects were not statistically significant. Together, the PCA results suggest that rhizospheric soil properties were governed predominantly by temporal changes associated with plant growth and rhizosphere development, while salinity and drought induced comparatively modest modifications to the overall physicochemical profile (Philippot et al., 2013).

Heatmap and Hierarchical Clustering Analysis

Hierarchical clustering revealed coordinated responses among specific groups of soil physicochemical properties. The close association of EC, OC, and K suggests that changes in soil ionic status were accompanied by alterations in carbon-related processes and potassium availability, particularly under salinity stress. Potassium is a key osmotic regulator in plants and its clustering with EC may reflect adaptive responses to osmotic and ionic stress conditions (Wang et al., 2013; Hasanuzzaman et al., 2018).

The clustering of pH, nitrogen and phosphorus indicates that nutrient availability and soil chemical balance remained closely linked across samples. Soil pH strongly influences nutrient

solubility and can affect microbial-mediated nutrient transformations, which may explain its association with nitrogen and phosphorus dynamics (Marschner, 2012; Paul, 2015). The absence of complete treatment-specific clustering suggests that salinity and drought modified particular soil properties without fundamentally restructuring the overall rhizospheric physicochemical profile.

The observed clustering patterns support the correlation and PCA analyses which identified EC, nutrient availability and carbon-related properties as major contributors to variation in the rhizosphere. Collectively, the results suggest that interactions among soil ionic status, nutrient availability and carbon-related processes were important contributors to rhizospheric soil variability in sorghum.

Conclusion

Developmental stage was the primary factor associated with variation in rhizospheric soil physicochemical properties of sorghum, explaining substantially more variability than salinity or drought treatments. Temporal changes in nutrient availability, electrical conductivity and organic carbon were evident throughout plant development, whereas treatment effects on the overall soil physicochemical profile were comparatively modest. Multivariate analyses identified pH, available nitrogen, electrical conductivity, organic carbon and potassium as major contributors to rhizospheric variability with a positive association between pH and nitrogen and coordinated variation among EC, OC and K. Phosphorus exhibited relatively independent variation. The findings indicate that developmental-stage-dependent changes were more strongly associated with rhizospheric soil variability than the imposed abiotic stress treatments.

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All the data is available in the manuscript and its supplementary files.

References

1. Abuslima, E., Kanbar, A., Raorane, M. L., Eiche, E., Junker, B. H., Hause, B., Riemann, M., & Nick, P. (2022). Gain time to adapt: How sorghum acquires tolerance to salinity. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 13, Article 1008172.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2022.1008172>
2. Ávila, R. G., Magalhães, P. C., Vitorino, L. C., Bessa, L. A., Souza, K. R. D. de, Queiroz, R. B., Jakelaitis, A., & Teixeira, M. B. (2023). Chitosan induces sorghum tolerance to

- water deficits by positively regulating photosynthesis and the production of primary metabolites, osmoregulators, and antioxidants. *Journal of Soil Science and Plant Nutrition*, 23(1), 1156–1172. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42729-022-01111-4>
3. Bekchanova, M., Champion, L., Bruns, S., Kuppens, T., Lehmann, J., & Jozefczak, M. (2024). Biochar improves the nutrient cycle in sandy-textured soils and increases crop yield: A systematic review. *Environmental Evidence*, 13, Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13750-024-00326-5>
 4. Bhaduri, D., Sihi, D., Bhowmik, A., & Verma, B. C. (2022). A review on effective soil health bio-indicators for ecosystem restoration and sustainability. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 13, Article 938481. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.938481>
 5. Bhattacharyya, S. S., & Furtak, K. (2023). Soil–plant–microbe interactions determine soil biological fertility by altering rhizospheric nutrient cycling and ecosystem functioning. *Sustainability*, 15(1), Article 625. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15010625>
 6. Brady, N. C., & Weil, R. R. (2016). *The nature and properties of soils* (15th ed.). Pearson.
 7. Dewi, E. S., Abdulai, I., Bracho-Mujica, G., Appiah, M., & Rötter, R. P. (2023). Agronomic and physiological traits response of tropical sorghum cultivars to drought and salinity. *Agronomy*, 13(11), Article 2788. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy13112788>
 8. Dourado, P. R. M., de Souza, E. R., dos Santos, M. A., Lins, C. M. T., Monteiro, D. R., Paulino, M. K. S. S., & Schaffer, B. (2022). Stomatal regulation and osmotic adjustment in sorghum in response to salinity. *Agriculture*, 12(5), Article 658. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture12050658>
 9. Drinkwater, L. E., & Snapp, S. S. (2022). Advancing the science and practice of ecological nutrient management for smallholder farmers. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 6, Article 921216. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2022.921216>
 10. Hanway, J. J., & Heidel, H. (1952). *Soil analysis methods as used in the Iowa State College Soil Testing Laboratory* (Iowa Agriculture Bulletin No. 57). Iowa State College, Agricultural Extension Service.

11. Harrell, F. E., Jr., & Dupont, C. (2020). *Hmisc: Harrell miscellaneous* (R package version 4.0) [Computer software]. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=Hmisc>
12. Hasanuzzaman, M., Bhuyan, M. B., Nahar, K., Hossain, M. S., Mahmud, J. A., Hossen, M. S., Masud, A. A. C., Moumita, & Fujita, M. (2018). Potassium: A vital regulator of plant responses and tolerance to abiotic stresses. *Agronomy*, 8(3), Article 31. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy8030031>
13. Hayashi, K. (2022). Nitrogen cycling and management focusing on the central role of soils: A review. *Soil Science and Plant Nutrition*, 68(5–6), 514–525. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00380768.2022.2125789>
14. Kassambara, A., & Mundt, F. (2016). *factoextra: Extract and visualize the results of multivariate data analyses* (Version 1.0.7) [R package]. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=factoextra>
15. Kolde, R. (2019). *pheatmap: Pretty heatmaps* (Version 1.0.12) [R package]. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=pheatmap>
16. Kunito, T., Moro, H., & Mise, K. (2024). Ecoenzymatic stoichiometry as a temporally integrated indicator of nutrient availability in soils. *Soil Science and Plant Nutrition*, 70(4), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00380768.2024.2341669>
17. Lê, S., Josse, J., & Husson, F. (2008). FactoMineR: An R package for multivariate analysis. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 25(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v025.i01>
18. Liu, F. (2015). *Electrical conductivity in soils: A review* [Preprint]. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.4868.2964>
19. Liu, S., He, F., Kuzyakov, Y., Xiao, H., Hoang, D. T. T., Pu, S., & Razavi, B. S. (2022). Nutrients in the rhizosphere: A meta-analysis of content, availability, and influencing factors. *Science of the Total Environment*, 826, Article 153908. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.153908>
20. Magdoff, F., & Weil, R. R. (2004). *Soil organic matter in sustainable agriculture*. CRC Press.

21. Marschner, P. (Ed.). (2012). *Marschner's mineral nutrition of higher plants* (3rd ed.). Academic Press.
22. Mishra, A. K., Das, R. R., Kerry, R. G., Biswal, B., Sinha, T., Sharma, S., Arora, P., & Kumar, M. (2022). Promising management strategies to improve crop sustainability and to amend soil salinity. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, *10*, Article 962581. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2022.962581>
23. Najdenko, E., Lorenz, F., Dittert, K., & Olf, H. W. (2024). Rapid in-field soil analysis of plant-available nutrients and pH for precision agriculture: A review. *Precision Agriculture*, *25*, 3189–3218. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11119-024-10181-6>
24. Neuwirth, E. (2014). *RColorBrewer: ColorBrewer palettes* (Version 1.1-2) [R package]. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=RColorBrewer>
25. Oksanen, J., Simpson, G. L., Blanchet, F. G., Kindt, R., Legendre, P., Minchin, P. R., O'Hara, R. B., Solymos, P., Stevens, M. H. H., Szoecs, E., & Wagner, H. (2001). *vegan: Community ecology package* (Version 2.6-10) [R package]. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=vegan>
26. Olsen, S. R. (1954). *Estimation of available phosphorus in soils by extraction with sodium bicarbonate* (U.S. Department of Agriculture Circular No. 939). U.S. Department of Agriculture. <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/doi/full/10.5555/19541901890>
27. Paul, E. A. (2015). Soil microbiology, ecology, and biochemistry: An exciting present and great future built on basic knowledge and unifying concepts. In E. A. Paul (Ed.), *Soil microbiology, ecology and biochemistry* (4th ed., pp. 1–15). Academic Press.
28. Philippot, L., Raaijmakers, J. M., Lemanceau, P., & Van der Putten, W. H. (2013). Going back to the roots: The microbial ecology of the rhizosphere. *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, *11*(11), 789–799. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrmicro3109>
29. Prashar, P., Kapoor, N., & Sachdeva, S. (2014). Rhizosphere: Its structure, bacterial diversity and significance. *Reviews in Environmental Science and Bio/Technology*, *13*(1), 63–77. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11157-013-9317-z>

30. Qi, M., Berry, J. C., Veley, K. M., O'Connor, L., Finkel, O. M., & Salas-González, I. (2022). Identification of beneficial and detrimental bacteria impacting sorghum responses to drought. *The ISME Journal*, *16*, 1957–1969. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41396-022-01245-4>
31. R Core Team. (2025). *R: A language and environment for statistical computing* [Computer software]. R Foundation for Statistical Computing. <https://www.R-project.org/>
32. Rajabi Dehnavi, A., Zahedi, M., & Piernik, A. (2024). Understanding salinity stress responses in sorghum: Exploring genotype variability and salt tolerance mechanisms. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, *14*, Article 1296286. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2023.1296286>
33. Rietz, D. N., & Haynes, R. J. (2003). Effects of irrigation-induced salinity and sodicity on soil microbial activity. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, *35*(6), 845–854. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717\(03\)00125-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717(03)00125-1)
34. Silva, R. R., Medeiros, J. F., Queiroz, G. C. M., Sousa, L. V., Souza, M. V. P., & Nascimento, M. A. B. (2023). Ionic response and sorghum production under water and saline stress in a semi-arid environment. *Agriculture*, *13*(6), Article 1127. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture13061127>
35. Song, X. D., Yang, F., Wu, H. Y., Zhang, J., Li, D. C., Liu, F., Zhao, Y. G., Yang, J. L., Ju, B., Cai, C. F., & Huang, B. (2022). Significant loss of soil inorganic carbon at the continental scale. *National Science Review*, *9*(2), Article nwab120. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nsr/nwab120>
36. Subbiah, B. V., & Asija, G. L. (1956). *A rapid procedure for the estimation of available nitrogen in soils*. <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/doi/full/10.5555/19571900070>
37. Walkley, A., & Black, I. A. (1934). An examination of the Degtjareff method for determining soil organic matter, and a proposed modification of the chromic acid titration method. *Soil Science*, *37*(1), 29–38.

38. Wang, M., Zheng, Q., Shen, Q., & Guo, S. (2013). The critical role of potassium in plant stress response. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, *14*(4), 7370–7390.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms14047370>
39. Wei, T., & Simko, V. (2010). *corrplot: Visualization of a correlation matrix* [R package].
<https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=corrplot>
40. Wei, Y., Yang, H., Hu, J., Li, H., Zhao, Z., Wu, Y., Li, J., Zhou, Y., & Yang, K. (2023). Trichoderma harzianum promotes sorghum growth in saline soil by modulating rhizosphere nutrients and microbial community. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, *14*, Article 1258131. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2023.1258131>
41. Weil, R. R., & Brady, N. C. (2016). *The nature and properties of soils* (15th ed.). Pearson.
42. Wickham, H., & Bryan, J. (2019). *readxl: Read Excel files* [R package].
<https://readxl.tidyverse.org>
43. Wickham, H. (2016). Data analysis. In *ggplot2: Elegant graphics for data analysis* (2nd ed., pp. 189–201). Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-24277-4>
44. Xing, L., Zhang, Y., Hu, C., Dong, W., Li, X., Liu, X., Zhang, L., & Wen, H. (2022). Effects of long-term nutrient recycling pathways on soil nutrient dynamics and fertility in farmland. *Chinese Journal of Eco-Agriculture*, *30*(6), 937–951.
<https://doi.org/10.12357/cjea.20220306>